

Synthesis of a Tridecasaccharide Lipooligosaccharide Antigen from the Opportunistic Pathogen *Mycobacterium kansasii*

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Abstract: The outer surfaces of mycobacteria, including the organism that causes tuberculosis, are decorated with an array of immunomodulatory glycans. Among these are lipooligosaccharides (LOS), a class of molecules for which the function remains poorly understood. We describe the chemical synthesis of the glycan portion of a tridecasaccharide LOS (**2**) from the opportunistic pathogen *Mycobacterium kansasii*. The target contains a number of unusual structural motifs that complicate its assembly. This report describes the first syntheses related to *M. kansasii* LOSs and **2** is the most complex mycobacterial LOS glycan to be synthesized to date when considering size and number of unique monosaccharides and glycosidic linkages. These studies not only provide a roadmap for the preparation of additional members of this family of glycans, but also provides a valuable probe for use in structure–activity relationship investigations

All mycobacteria, including the causative agent of tuberculosis, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, possess a glycan-rich cell wall that protects these organisms from their environment.^[1] In addition to playing an important structural role in cell wall integrity, these glycans assist in evasion of the host immune system.^[2] A broad range of glycan classes is present in the mycobacterial cell wall, including polysaccharides and glycolipids.^[2–3] Despite their demonstrated roles in influencing the progression of mycobacterial disease, a molecular-level understanding of how many of these glycans exert their effects is lacking. This deficiency is due in large part to a scarcity of

structurally-defined chemical tools that can be used to interrogate these processes.

Arguably the least studied of the mycobacterial cell wall glycans are the lipooligosaccharides (LOSs), which are produced by a host of different mycobacteria, including some strains of *M. tuberculosis*.^[4] All LOS possess a trehalose core (**1**, Figure 1) that is further functionalized with a species-specific glycan and 2–4 acyl groups.^[4–5] These glycolipids are potent antigens^[5–6] and they have a role in biofilm formation.^[7] Beyond their ability to act as antigens, their other immunomodulatory effects remain unclear and published studies often report conflicting data.^[8] Access to well-defined mycobacterial LOSs, and their fragments and analogs, would enable much more informative studies and structure–activity relationships to be performed. Such compounds are most conveniently accessed by chemical synthesis. However, the synthesis of mycobacterial LOSs has been the subject of only a few reported investigations.^[9] In particular, the syntheses of the complete glycan domains of only two mycobacterial LOS, have been described.^[9a, 9e] We describe here the synthesis tridecasaccharide **2**, which corresponds to the glycan portion of the largest LOSs produced by the opportunistic pathogen *Mycobacterium kansasii*.^[4, 10] This is the largest and most complex mycobacterial LOS glycan for which the synthesis has been reported with regard to number of different monosaccharides and glycosidic linkages.

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Figure 1. Structures of trehalose (**1**), highlighting its modifications when present as a constituent of mycobacterial LOS, and the *M. kansasii* LOS-related target **2**, the synthesis of which is described in this paper.

The number of unusual structural motifs in **2** make it a formidable synthetic target. These include an asymmetrically-substituted trehalose residue,^[11] a branched-chain aminosugar *N*-acylated with an epimerizable α -substituted propanoic acid derivative, an *L*-xylan domain, and *D*-fucose and methylated *L*-rhamnose residues. This work not only provides an important probe molecule, but also lays out the first strategy to access other structurally-related LOS from *M. kansasii*, which all share the α -*L*-Rhap-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -*D*-GlcP-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -*D*-GlcP-(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -*D*-GlcP-(1 \leftrightarrow 1)- α -*D*-GlcP pentasaccharide motif present in **2**. The target was synthesized with an 8-aminoctanamide group on one of the primary carbons of the trehalose moiety. This was done both to mimic the acyl group present in the natural compounds and to provide a reactive handle that would allow its facile conjugation to other materials, e.g., proteins for antibody generation or a glycan array surface.^[12] An amide linkage was chosen to attach this group to the glycan to ensure long term stability compared to the native ester.

We envisioned that **2** could be produced from a series of mono- and disaccharide building blocks **3–7** (Scheme 1). The general approach was to build up the oligosaccharide starting from the trehalose end of the molecule and then functionalize it with an 8-azidoctanamide linker before deprotection. Disaccharide **3**, which was obtained by desymmetrizing commercially-available trehalose, and monosaccharide **4** were prepared as described in the Supporting Information (Figure S1). The synthesis of **5–7** is described below.

Scheme 1. Retrosynthetic analysis of **2**.

The synthesis of disaccharide **5** made use of two thioglycoside building blocks: **8** (see Scheme S2A for its synthesis in 10 steps from *D*-rhamnose) and **9**, which was obtained in five steps from *D*-glucose.^[13] The strategy was to rely on the armed nature of **8** compared to **9**, due to C-6 deoxygenation and the lack of a torsionally-deactivating benzylidene acetal (Scheme 2), to allow their selective coupling. The reaction was initiated by treatment of the two compounds at -30 °C with *N*-iodosuccinimide

(NIS) and trimethylsilyl trifluoromethanesulfonate (TMSOTf) and the reaction was warmed over one hour to -20 °C. Under these conditions, rhamnose-thioglycoside **8** was, as hoped, activated in preference to **9** and the expected disaccharide thioglycoside **5** was obtained in 88% yield. The $^1J_{C1-H1}$ of the rhamnosidic bond in **5** was 174.1 Hz, confirming the α -stereochemistry.^[14]

Scheme 2. Synthesis of **5** via chemoselective glycosylation.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of disaccharide **6** and tetrasaccharide **21**.

The construction of the β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-linked *L*-xylobiose disaccharide **6** is shown in Scheme 3. Although commercially available, *L*-xylose (**10**) is very expensive and, as such, it was prepared in multigram scale from *D*-glucose as reported.^[15] Subsequent debenzoylation gave a high yield of triol **13**. Our initial

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design involved selective protection of the C-4 hydroxyl group as a trichloroethoxycarbonate (Troc) group. Thus, **13** was converted into **15** in two steps and 86% overall yield by first regioselective tin-mediated acylation (to give **14**) and then benzylation. Thioglycoside **15** could be obtained in good yield; however, its use in glycosylation reactions (not shown) provided complex reaction mixtures that were difficult to purify and the desired products could only be obtained in poor-to-modest yield. In search of a solution, we prepared levulinate (Lev) ester **17** by first treatment of **15** with zinc and acetic acid and then Steglich esterification (86% overall yield).

We were pleased to find that **17** could be converted cleanly into its corresponding trichloroacetimidate (TCA) derivative by first *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS)-mediated thioglycoside hydrolysis and then treatment of the product hemiacetal with 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (DBU) and trichloroacetonitrile. Once produced, this activatable derivative could be used to glycosylate **16** upon treatment with TMSOTf. The product, **6**, was obtained in 64% yield over the three steps. In the ^1H NMR spectrum of **6**, we were surprised to find that the $^3J_{1,2}$ of the nonreducing residue H-1 resonance was 5.5 Hz, smaller than expected for a β -xylopyranoside. The other coupling constants in this ring were also usual ($^3J_{2,3} = 7.6$ Hz, $^3J_{3,4} = 7.4$ Hz). Similar values also were seen in the reducing end residue ($^3J_{1,2} = 7.2$ Hz, $^3J_{2,3} = 8.1$ Hz, $^3J_{3,4} = 8.0$ Hz). The xylopyranose ring is known to be conformationally flexible^[16] presumably in part because it lacks a C-5 hydroxymethyl group.^[17] Therefore, we postulated that this residue adopts a conformation other than $^4\text{C}_1$ or was present as a mixture of conformers, possibly due to steric congestion between the O-2 benzoate and the aglycone. To test this hypothesis, we deacylated **6**. In the ^1H NMR spectrum of the product (**18**, Scheme 3) the $^3J_{1,2}$ values of the H-1 resonances were 7.5 Hz (non-reducing end) and 9.2 Hz (reducing end), which are values more typical of 1,2-*trans* pyranosides and thiopyranosides, respectively. Thus, it appears that benzylation of O-2 (and possibly a coordinated effect by benzylation at O-3 and O-4) leads to a conformational change thus complicating analysis of molecules with these residues. These anomalous coupling constants were observed in all of the O-2 benzoylated xylopyranose rings in the larger oligomers.

To increase the convergence of the synthesis (see below) we also prepared a L-xylose homotetrasaccharide activated as a donor. Disaccharide **6** was thus either deprotected to give alcohol **19** (93% yield) or was converted into trichloroacetimidate **20** via NBS-mediated hydrolysis and then treatment of the resulting hemiacetal with trichloroacetonitrile and DBU. Subsequent coupling of **19** and **20** mediated by TMSOTf provided the required tetrasaccharide thioglycoside **21** in 77% overall yield from **6**. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **6** revealed that all of the $^3J_{1,2}$ values of the O-glycosidic linkages were between 5.5 Hz and 6.3 Hz, which, based on the discussion above, is consistent with the β -stereochemistry.

The preparation of the final disaccharide building block (**7**, Scheme 4) began with the previously reported aminosugar **22** (obtained in eight steps from L-rhamnose)^[18] and (*R*)-2-methoxypropanoic acid (**23**, see Scheme S2B for its synthesis), which were coupled using 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-carbodiimide (EDCI) in 92% yield. The isopropylidene ketal in **24** was hydrolyzed under acidic conditions to give a 90% yield of diol **25**, which was selectively methylated on the C-2 hydroxyl group using silver oxide as the base. This reaction provided an 88%

yield of **26**. Other bases were explored for this transformation, but the regioselectivity of the methylation was poor and epimerization of the stereocenter in the amide side-chain occurred. Treatment of this compound with acetic acid, acetic anhydride and sulfuric acid gave, in 80% yield, **27** in which the tertiary alcohol was acetylated and the methyl glycoside was converted to a glycosyl acetate. Selective cleavage of the anomeric acetate in **27** followed by treatment with cesium carbonate and trichloroacetonitrile, provided the corresponding glycosyl imidate that was in turn used to glycosylate alcohol **28** (see Scheme S2C for its synthesis in six steps from D-fucose) under the promotion of TMSOTf. The desired disaccharide product **7** was obtained in 55% yield over the three steps. The $^1J_{\text{C-1,H-1}}$ of H-1 of the newly introduced glycoside bond was 171.9 Hz, consistent with the α -stereochemistry.

Scheme 4. Synthesis of disaccharide **7**.

Armed with all of the required building blocks, we embarked on the synthesis of tridecasaccharide **2** (Scheme 5). Thus, glycosylation of **3** with **4** using NIS and TMSOTf as the promoter provided the expected trisaccharide **29** in 91% yield. Removal of the levulinate ester in 94% yield was achieved upon treatment with hydrazine acetate, affording trisaccharide alcohol **30**. Glycosylation of **30** with disaccharide **5**, again promoted by NIS and TMSOTf led to the formation of pentasaccharide **31** in 88% yield.

Pentasaccharide **31** was desilylated using tetra-*n*-butylammonium fluoride in 95% yield providing alcohol **32**, which was glycosylated with disaccharide **6** promoted by NIS and TMSOTf affording **33** in 92% yield. With **33** in hand, it was incorporated into a sequence leading to the final target compound. Treatment of **33** with hydrazine acetate gave an 86% yield of alcohol **34**, which underwent glycosylation with **21** mediated by

Scheme 5. Synthesis of tridecasaccharide 2.

NIS and TMSOTf producing undecasaccharide in 86% yield. The Lev group was removed and the resulting product was then coupled with disaccharide thioglycoside **7**, leading to tridecasaccharide **37** in 83% yield over the two steps. Reduction of the azide under Staudinger conditions with trimethylphosphine provided **38**, which was then then coupled with 8-azidoctanoic acid (**39**, see Scheme S2D for its synthesis) using 2-(1H-benzotriazole-1-yl)-1,1,3,3-tetramethylammonium tetrafluoroborate (TBTU). The resulting amide product **40** was obtained in 90% yield over the two steps. The use of trimethylphosphine in the Staudinger reduction, as opposed to the more common triphenylphosphine, was because the phosphine oxide by-product could be easily removed by extraction.

To accomplish the deprotection of **40**, the correct reaction conditions were critical. In particular, it was found that the stereogenic center on the propanamide side chain of the terminal

monosaccharide epimerized if treated under strongly basic conditions (see discussion above). Thus, when removing the benzoyl and acetyl groups using sodium methoxide, it was necessary to maintain the solution pH below 9. At the same time, if the reaction was done at room temperature, the cleavage of the benzoate esters was very slow. As such, it was necessary to perform the reaction at 40 °C, while checking the pH periodically adding base as necessary. Once the acyl groups were cleaved, we attempted to cleave the benzylidene acetals under standard acidic conditions (4:1 HOAc–H₂O, 80 °C). However, decomposition of the molecule was observed. Therefore, this transformation was carried out, together with cleavage of the benzyl ethers, using hydrogenation over palladium hydroxide in a mixture of methanol, water and acetic acid. These conditions also reduced the azide to the amine. In addition to **2**, we found that a partially *N*-methylated product was produced if the hydrogenation

step was extended. This product presumably results from trace amounts of formaldehyde in the methanol reacting with the amine to form an imine that is subsequently reduced. The purification of **2** proved to be problematic. Use of either normal phase or reversed phase chromatography was not successful, but purification could be achieved using gel filtration chromatography (Sephadex, LH-20). By implementing this approach, tridecasaccharide **2** was obtained in 81% yield over the two-step deprotection protocol.

In conclusion, we have established a strategy for the synthesis of *M. kansasii* LOS glycans and demonstrated its efficacy via the synthesis of the largest member of this family of molecules, tridecasaccharide **2**. This work represents the first total syntheses of glycan domains of *M. kansasii* LOSs and **2** is the most complex mycobacterial LOS-related molecule to have been synthesized to date. The strategy to **2** employed a key 7 + 4 + 2 glycosylation sequence to link the carbohydrate residues and involved iterative NIS-TMSOTf promoted glycosylations of thioglycoside donors and levulinate ester deprotections. Among the challenges to be overcome were: 1) the synthesis of an asymmetrically substituted trehalose moiety, which was achieved using desymmetrization of trehalose; 2) the installation of a rare branched chain sugar with an amide substituent containing an epimerizable group and 3) unexpected conformational effects in the L-xylopyranoside rings in protected intermediates, which complicated their analysis. The compound was synthesized with an 8-aminooctamide moiety to allow its straightforward coupling to other species. Indeed, **2** was coupled via a squaramide linker^[19] to bovine serum albumin with a loading of nine glycans/protein (see Supporting Information). Not only has this work provided a strategy to allow the synthesis of other members of this family of glycans, which all share a common pentasaccharide core (α -L-Rhap-(1→4)- β -D-Glcp-(1→4)- β -D-Glcp-(1→4)- α -D-Glcp-(1→1)- α -D-Glcp) but both the protein conjugate and the free glycan are valuable chemical probes. To that end, compound **2**, and has been incorporated into a mycobacterial glycan array, which is increasingly being shown to be an important tool in characterizing lectins of the human innate immune system and monoclonal antibodies.^{[12] [20]}

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, the Canadian Institutes of Health Research and the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada

Keywords: Lipooligosaccharide • synthesis • mycobacteria • antigen • complex glycan

References

- [1] C. L. Dulberger, E. J. Rubin, C. C. Boutte, *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **2020**, *18*, 47–59.
- [2] S. M. Batt, D. E. Minnikin, G. S. Besra, *Biochem. J.* **2020**, *477*, 1983–2006.
- [3] S. K. Angala, J. M. Belardinelli, E. Huc-Claustre, W. H. Wheat, M. Jackson, *Crit. Rev. Biochem. Mol. Biol.* **2014**, *49*, 361–399.
- [4] B. Bai, C.-J. Chu, T. L. Lowary, *Isr. J. Chem.* **2015**, *55*, 360–372.
- [5] D. E. Minnikin, P. J. Brennan, in *Health Consequences of Microbial Interactions with Hydrocarbons, Oils, and Lipids. Handbook of Hydrocarbon and Lipid Microbiology.*, Vol. 35 (Ed.: G. H.), Springer International Publishing, Cham, **2020**, pp. 33–108.
- [6] M. Daffé, D. C. Crick, M. Jackson, *Microbiol. Spectr.* **2014**, *2*, 1–46.
- [7] H. Ren, L. Dover, S. Islam, D. Alexander, J. Chen, G. Besra, J. Liu, *Mol. Microbiol.* **2007**, *63*, 1345–1359.
- [8] a) F. M. Collins, D. S. Cunningham, *Infect. Immun.* **1981**, *32*, 614–624; b) L. Alibaud, J. Pawelczyk, L. Gannoun-Zaki, V. K. Singh, Y. Rombouts, M. Drancourt, J. Dziadek, Y. Guerardel, L. Kremer, *J. Biol. Chem.* **2014**, *289*, 215–228; c) I. Szulc-Kielbik, J. Pawelczyk, M. Kielbik, L. Kremer, J. Dziadek, M. Klink, *Microb. Cell Fact.* **2017**, *1*–11.
- [9] a) T. Ziegler, E. Eckhardt, V. Birault, *J. Org. Chem.* **1993**, *58*, 1090–1099; b) C. Mukherjee, A. K. Misra, *Glycoconjugate J.* **2008**, *25*, 611–624; c) R. Panchadhayee, A. K. Misra, *Glycoconjugate J.* **2008**, *25*, 817–826; d) L. Wang, M. Dong, T. L. Lowary, *J. Org. Chem.* **2015**, *80*, 2767–2780; e) M. A. Chaube, S. S. Kulkarni, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2015**, *21*, 13544–13548; f) T. Hansen, T. P. Ofman, J. G. C. Vlaming, I. A. Gagarinov, J. Beek, T. A. Goté, J. M. Tichem, G. Ruijgrok, H. S. Overkleeft, D. V. Filippov, G. A. Marel, J. D. C. Codée, *Angew. Chem. Intl. Ed.* **2021**, *60*, 937–945.
- [10] a) J.-J. Fournie, M. Riviere, G. Puzo, *J. Biol. Chem.* **1987**, *262*, 3174–3179; b) S. W. Hunter, T. Fujiwara, R. C. Murphy, P. J. Brennan, *J. Biol. Chem.* **1984**, *259*, 9729–9734.
- [11] a) C.-H. Wu, C.-C. Wang, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2014**, *12*, 5558–5562; b) S. Jana, S. S. Kulkarni, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2020**, *18*, 2013–2037.
- [12] R. B. Zheng, S. A. F. Jégouzo, M. Joe, Y. Bai, H.-A. Tran, K. Shen, J. Saupe, L. Xia, M. F. Ahmed, Y.-H. Liu, P. S. Patil, A. Tripathi, S.-C. Hung, M. E. Taylor, T. L. Lowary, K. Drickamer, *ACS Chem. Biol.* **2017**, *12*, 2990–3002.
- [13] X. Zhou, Q. Long, D. Li, J. Gao, Q. Sun, S. Sun, Y. Su, P. Wang, W. Peng, M. Li, *Synthesis* **2021**, *53*, 2435–2448.
- [14] K. Bock, C. Pedersen, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2* **1974**, 293–297.
- [15] R. K. Ness, *Methods Carbohydr. Chem.* **1962**, *1*, 90–93.
- [16] C. V. Holland, D. Horton, J. S. Jewell, *J. Org. Chem.* **1967**, *32*, 1818–1821.
- [17] M. K. Dowd, W. M. Rockey, A. D. French, P. J. Reilly, *J. Carbohydr. Chem.* **2002**, *21*, 11–25.
- [18] a) J. Yoshimura, A. Aqeel, K.-I. Sato, R. Bir Singh, H. Hashimoto, *Carbohydr. Res.* **1987**, *166*, 253–262; b) J. Yoshimura, K.-I. Sato, A. Aqeel, R. B. Singh, H. Hashimoto, *Carbohydr. Res.* **1985**, *144*, C15–C17.
- [19] V. P. Kamath, P. Diedrich, O. Hindsgaul, *Glycoconjugate J.* **1996**, *13*, 315–319.
- [20] A. Choudhary, D. Patel, R. S. Prattipati, R. B. Zheng, Y.-C. Hsueh, M. L. Gennaro, A. Lardizabal, B. I. Restrepo, M. Garcia-Viveros, M. Joe, Y. Bai, K. Shen, K. Sahloul, J. S. Spencer, D. Chatterjee, T. Broger, T. L. Lowary, A. Pinter, *J. Immunol.* **2018**, 3053–3066.

